

GRAPHENE-ENHANCED COMPOSITE PAINTS FOR CORROSION PROTECTION OF OFFSHORE RISER

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ABSTRACT

Graphene flakes with thicknesses of less than 1 nm were dispersed in the epoxy paint to study the efficacy of graphene as a barrier additives. A blending protocol based on planetary mixing was established to obtain a homogeneous distribution and dispersion of the graphene in the paint. Two graphene loadings of 0.01 and 0.05 wt% were investigated. The blended paint was applied on steel substrate with nominal dry film thickness of 400 μm . Overall, the incorporation of graphene was revealed to produce improved corrosion performance as demonstrated by electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and salt spray exposure. By means of adhesion tests, it was revealed that the bonding between the paint coating and the substrate was enhanced by the graphene additions in the paint. This proves the graphene present in the paint is advantageous for preventing any occurrence of corrosion underneath the coating and subsequent onset of blistering. Graphene added to the paint, however, did not seem to make any difference in durability of the paint against UV exposure, and this could possibly be due to lesser of graphene loading used in this work.

1 INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is among the key challenges faced by the oil and gas industry because it has a significant impact on the integrity of major infrastructures such as pipelines and risers. Harsh environments and long-term exposure are the two main contributors to corrosion of these metallic components that would eventually, and prematurely, reduce life of these assets [1, 2]. To overcome corrosion, polymer coatings have widely been used to protect metallic components and structures, where epoxy and polyurethane paint systems are the most commonly used.

The introduction of glass flakes (GF) as a filler in commercial epoxy paints is one of the most common strategies used to enhance barrier performance whereby the flakes would increase path tortuosity for the corrosion species to diffuse through the coating. Based on the same notion, graphene has more recently been studied as a potential filler for paint but with added advantages [3]. Due to its much higher aspect ratio and surface area, graphene sheets have the potential to provide better barrier performance to the coating, compared with other nanomaterials [3]. However, introducing this type of materials in the coating system is expected to affect other properties, such as physical, chemical, mechanical and thermal properties. Wang *et al.* [1] investigated the effect of graphene in epoxy resin as a protective coating for oil and gas pipeline applications. The study revealed that the graphene enhanced corrosion resistant and mechanical properties of the epoxy coating. However higher loading led to particle agglomeration and disrupted the performance of the epoxy as a barrier coating. In another study by Liu *et al.* [4] on the effects of graphene on tribology and corrosion performance of the coating disclosed that these properties are severely degraded when the graphene concentration is higher than 0.5 wt%.

The corrosion resistance of nano-enhanced coatings are clearly not only influenced by the types of environment and substrate, but also the composition of the nano-enhanced coatings, further investigation on the effect of graphene in fully formulated epoxy paint is warranted. Thus, in this work, two different graphene concentrations at 0.01 and 0.05 wt% in a commercially available epoxy paint commonly used for offshore risers were studied. The effects of the graphene in the paint were

experimentally evaluated using the electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), pull-off adhesion strength and abrasion tests. Long-term performance of the coating was also investigated by accelerated exposure to ultraviolet (UV) and salt spray.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The nanoflakes used in the present work is a commercial grade graphene with nominal thickness of < 1 nm, as given in the product datasheet. The paint used is a commercially available splash zone protective coating for offshore and marine applications. The epoxy paint has a high glass flake concentration of ~ 60 wt% that constitute an overall solid content of approximately 92%. The mass ratio between the resin and curing agent is 4:1. The metal substrate used is A36 carbon steel plates with thickness of 2.5 mm. The surfaces of steel were prepared for coating as recommended for field application, *viz.* sand blasting to get SA 2.5 surface profile, then cleaned with acetone before finally application of the paint.

For all the tests considered in this work, the graphene-modified paints are evaluated against the equivalent, unmodified, neat paint.

2.2 Graphene/epoxy coating preparation

The graphene is mixed with the epoxy paint using a planetary mixer. Two graphene concentrations of 0.01 and 0.05 wt% were used in this work. Once blending is completed, the curing agent is added and stirred manually for another 10 minutes. The graphene-modified paint is finally applied on carbon steel plate using 400 μm thickness bar coater (RK Printcoats Instruments). The paint coatings are then allowed to cure at room temperature for a week before testing. The thickness of the cured paint coatings is measured using an Elcometer dry film thickness instrument.

2.3 Characterisation

a. Electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

The barrier performance of the paint coatings is evaluated by EIS, according to ISO 16773 [5]. A conventional three electrode cell is employed for electrochemical measurement in 3.5 wt% NaCl solution with the substrate acting as a working electrode, saturated calomel as a reference and platinum mesh as the counter electrode. The amplitude of sinusoidal signal is 10 mV, and the frequency ranging from 10^{-2} to 10^5 Hz. The test is performed on specimens exposed to UV and to salt spray for and the results are worked out using the Bode plot, in conjunction with the Gamry software.

b. Adhesion test

Pull-off adhesion tests are performed according to ASTM D4541 [6] to evaluate the adhesion strength between paint coating and the substrate. Aluminium dollies with a diameter of 20mm are glued on the surface of paint, and left to cure at room temperature for 24 hours. The pull-off tests are carried out, in triplicate, at a pulling rate of 1 MPa/s, using the Positest AT-A, Defelsko.

c. Abrasion test

Abrasion tests are carried out in according with ASTM D4060 [7] using Taber Abraser 5150 machine. A 1kg of load was applied on the graphene epoxy paint surface for 1000 cycles. Abrading wheel CS-10 grade composed of a resilient binder, and aluminium oxide or silicon carbide abrasive particles was used for this abrasion resistance study. Weight of the coated specimens before and after the abrasion test are measured to calculate the mass loss due to abrasion.

d. Accelerated ultra violet (UV) aging test

UV resistance of the paint coating is evaluated by exposing specimens to a Q-Lab UV environmental chamber. The test is carried out according to ASTM D4587-09 [8], which prescribes the standard procedure for UV-condensation exposures of paints, and related, coatings. By means of UVA-340 lamps the paint coatings are exposed to 4 hours of UV, followed by 4 hours of condensation, and the cycle is repeated for a total of 288 hours. The temperature is maintained at 60°C with the irradiation set at 0.89 W/ (m² nm). The surface layer of the paint coatings are analysed with Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR) in ATR (Attenuated Total Reflection) mode to investigate the spectrum peak intensity of the O-ring, both before and after UV exposure. This analyses are carried out using a Perkin Elmer FTIR Spectrum 400, in conjunction with a proprietary spectrum software.

e. Salt spray test

The corrosion resistance of the paint coatings is investigated using a salt spray test in accordance with ASTM B117 [9]. Prior to exposure, scribes are created on the surface of the specimens using a pen knife of 0.5 mm blade thickness. Specimens are placed in the salt spray chamber at 35°C with continuous spray of NaCl solution (5.0 wt%, pH = 6.5 - 7.0). Three specimens were carried out in parallel for all samples. The specimens are left in the conditioning chamber for up to 1440 hours. Visual inspection of the coatings surface are carried out at the end of the test period to inspect for any defect present such as blister, rust and loss of adhesion.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Barrier performance

EIS is a common technique that is widely used to study the electrochemical activity in order to assess the corrosion behaviour of a coated substrate [1, 2, and 10]. Technically, the EIS test measures electrochemical impedance, which corresponds to the ability of the coating to resist current flow. Increasing impedance suggests improvement in barrier performance of the coating. In this work, EIS results are presented by means of the Bode plot diagram, as displayed in Figures 1 to 3.

From the figures, it can be observed that neat, *i.e.* unmodified, epoxy paint has reducing impedance with increasing exposure time, particularly after 48 hours, which is consistent with greater permeation rate of the electrolyte solution into the paint coating. On the contrary, the impedance for the 0.01 and 0.05 wt% graphene-modified paint remained stable at approximately 10⁷ Ω up through the tests right up to 168 hours of exposure. In fact, no loss of adhesion and no blistering on the paint surface have been observed. The improvement in the electrochemical impedance or water permeation resistance can be explained by the presence of graphene as an impermeable material. The 2D structure and thin layer of the graphene successfully formed a more tortuous path for the diffusion of oxygen and moisture to reduce the traverse of electrolyte into, and through, the paint coatings.

3.2 Adhesion strength

Figure 4 shows the adhesion strength of the epoxy paint coatings as a function of graphene concentration. Compared to the neat paint coating, adhesion strength has been observed to increase significantly, by some 50%, with the addition of 0.05 wt% graphene. However, results of the 0.01 wt% graphene-modified paint coating did not reveal any appreciable improvement in adhesion performance. More study is required to fully understand the role played by graphene in enhancing the adhesion between paint coatings and their substrate, but other researchers have suggested that graphene helps to reduce porosity at the interface as one possible factor [11, 12].

Figure 1: EIS result of the neat/unmodified epoxy paint.

Figure 2: EIS result of 0.01 wt% graphene-modified epoxy paint.

Figure 3: EIS result of 0.01 wt% graphene-modified epoxy paint.

Figure 4: Adhesion strength of the various paint coatings investigated in this work.

Figure 5: Abrasion performance of the various paint coatings investigated in this work.

3.3 Abrasion resistance

The abrasion resistance of the paint coatings is related to weight loss due to continuous abrading the surface with a standard abramer. Good abrasion resistance is desirable for a protective coating to ensure it is durable in services. Figure 5 summarises the abrasion resistance of the neat and graphene-modified paint coatings. It can be seen that the incorporation of graphene can reduce the mass loss of the paint coatings, even at the lower concentration of 0.01 wt% of graphene. Even better resistance is recorded in the 0.05 wt% graphene-modified paint, whereby the mass loss is only about a third of that of the neat paint coating. This result correlated well with the recent work of Zhang *et al.* [13, 14] on similar graphene epoxy coatings. Their study of coefficient of friction and wear rate found gradual reduction in both properties as the loading of graphene is increased. They attributed their findings to possible self-lubrication effect of graphene by forming stable graphene-polymer films between the contact surfaces, thus resulting in reduced friction.

3.4 UV resistance

In Figure 6, it can be seen that long-term UV exposure of all three paint coatings (*i.e.* neat, and 0.01 wt% and 0.05 wt% graphene-modified) results in large increments in the carbonyl peak (C=O) intensity, as represented in the spectrum peak of 1722 cm^{-1} (circled in red line). The incorporation of graphene appears not to have any appreciable effect on UV degradation of the paints. The formation of these oxidation products is in good agreement with a photo-oxidative studies that were previously published [15, 16]. It is also found that the alkyl group peak represented by spectrum peak of $2800\text{-}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (pointed by red arrow) is decreased after UV exposure. It is believed that, in the presence of UV radiation, the alkyl chain C-H and CH_2 groups will form the carbonyl group due to reaction with oxygen. For added clarity, a close-up view of the carbonyl spectrum at 1722 cm^{-1} is shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that both the unexposed neat and graphene-modified paint coatings do not have carbonyl peak present, while there is an obvious increment in this same peak for all the specimens that have been exposed for 288 hours. It is highly possible that lower of graphene loading used might result no appreciable difference between the neat and graphene-modified paint coatings is detected. Further work involving higher loading of graphene and much longer exposure times will be carried out later.

Figure 6: FTIR spectra of paint coatings before and after accelerated 288 hours of UV exposure.
Unexposed: 1) Neat, 2) 0.05 wt% graphene-modified.
UV exposed: 3) Neat, 4) 0.05 wt% graphene-modified and 5) 0.01 wt% graphene-modified.

Figure 7: Close-up view of carbonyl peaks of the paint coatings, before and after 288 hours UV exposure.

3.5 Corrosion resistance

Only the 0.05 wt% graphene-modified, and the neat, paint coatings are considered for the salt spray test. From Figure 8, it can be deduced that the graphene specimen outperforms its neat counterpart, for corrosion resistance. In the latter, rust residue is observed, and corrosion underneath the paint coating has clearly set in already, in some cases severely enough to cause blistering. This result is consistent with the conclusions drawn from EIS, which indicates that the addition of graphene to the paint effectively increases barrier performance, thus hindering the corrosion process. Similarly, better adhesion observed for the graphene-modified paint coatings would explain the absence of corrosion underneath the coating and blistering.

Figure 8: Salt spray results of the neat and graphene-modified paint coatings, after 1440 hours of exposure.

Another point that is worth highlighting is incorporation of graphene may result in reduction of water contact due to hydrophobicity behavior of the graphene, and this could have also contributed in the observed better corrosion performance. Similar findings, which demonstrated an increased in contact angle for the epoxy coating mixed with graphene [17], supports the notion that water interaction is affected by the graphene nanomaterial.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the performance of the graphene-modified epoxy paints was assessed by studying its effect on corrosion resistance, adhesion strength to substrate, and long-term durability to UV exposure. Overall, the incorporation of graphene was revealed to produce improved corrosion performance as demonstrated by electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and salt spray exposure. By means of adhesion tests, it was revealed that the bonding between the paint coating and the substrate was enhanced by the graphene additions in the paint. This proves the graphene present in the paint is advantageous for preventing any occurrence of corrosion underneath the coating and subsequent onset of blistering. Graphene added to the paint, however, did not seem to make any difference in durability of the paint against UV exposure, and this is possibly due to the inherently good UV resistance of the (neat) paint to start with.

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